

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Exploring the Rational Design and Strategy of Metal Ion-Integrated 3D Hierarchical Spinel Oxide Nano/Microarchitecture for Battery-Supercapacitor Hybrid Energy Storage System

Periyasamy Sivakumar¹ | C. Justin Raj² | Palaniappan Subramanian³ | Antonysamy Dennyson Savariraj¹ | Ramu Manikandan⁴ | Priti Singh⁵ | Mudit Dixit^{5,6} | Hyun Jung¹

¹Department of Chemistry, Advanced Functional Nanohybrid Material Laboratory, Dongguk University - Seoul Campus, Seoul, Republic of Korea |

²Department of Physics, School of Advanced Sciences, Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT), Chennai Campus, Chennai, India | ³New Technologies - Research Center, University of West Bohemia, Plzeň, Czech | ⁴Department of Energy and Materials Engineering, Dongguk University - Seoul Campus, Seoul, Republic of Korea | ⁵CSIR-Central Leather Research Institute (CSIR-CLRI), Chennai, India | ⁶Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), Ghaziabad, India

Correspondence: Hyun Jung (chemphile@dongguk.edu)

Received: 17 September 2025 | **Revised:** 29 October 2025 | **Accepted:** 6 November 2025

Keywords: battery-supercapacitor hybrid system | DFT calculation | metal ion-integrated spinel oxide | nano/microarchitecture | synergistic effect

ABSTRACT

The synergistic interaction and strategic manipulation of electronic structures by incorporating metal ions into the host matrix have captivated research efforts for supercapacitors. This study presents an efficient strategy for synthesizing Cu-ion-incorporated NiCo₂O₄ (CNCO) nano/microarchitectures using a hydrothermal method followed by heat treatment. It establishes a clear link between variations in Cu content and their effects on material properties, which influence electrochemical performance. Optimizing the Cu content enhances ion transport and conductivity, while creating active sites for faster charge transfer. The porous framework boosts structural integrity and mass transport, reducing aggregation risks. Enhanced performance stems from synergistic interactions between Cu and the NCO matrix in the CNCO nano/microarchitecture. The experimental findings are further substantiated by computational analyses utilizing density functional theory (DFT) calculations. Impressively, the regulated CNCO electrode material exhibits a remarkable specific capacitance of 1301 F/g at 1 A/g and a rate capability of 81.3% at 20 A/g, significantly outperforming other CNCO variants. The optimized CNCO electrode material contributes to a high-performance battery-supercapacitor hybrid system, achieving an energy density of 61.36 Wh/kg at a power density of 1.18 kW/kg, with excellent cyclic stability. This system illuminates green and pink light-emitting diodes.

1 | Introduction

As environmental challenges and energy demand rise, there is an urgent need to harness renewable energy sources, which are often intermittent, driving accelerated development of reliable energy storage systems [1–3]. Supercapacitors (SCs) are a promising energy storage solution that combines the benefits of both batteries and traditional capacitors, offering a balance between

high energy density and elevated power density [4, 5]. Their rapid charging and discharging rates, long lifespan, enhanced safety, cost-effectiveness, and eco-friendly nature have increased their popularity as viable energy storage systems [6, 7]. The pursuit of better energy density, constrained by charge storage capacity and voltage performance, presents significant challenges in the field [8]. To enhance energy density in supercapacitors (SCs), combining capacitive and redox-type systems creates a hybrid

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2025 The Author(s). *Small Structures* published by Wiley-VCH GmbH.

configuration known as battery-SC systems (BSHs) [9]. The BSH system leverages the synergistic properties of its electrodes, yielding higher operating potentials and enhanced capacitance performance. This results in improved energy density while maintaining rate capability, power density, and cycling stability [10]. In capacitive-type electrodes, energy is stored by accumulating electrostatic charge at the interfaces, whereas in battery-type systems, it occurs through reversible Faradic redox reactions with active materials [11, 12]. Therefore, developing electrode materials with intrinsic synergistic properties is crucial for improving SC performance with key properties including a structured design, ample active sites, and high conductivity [13–15].

In the realm of active electrode materials, nanostructured metal oxides exhibit exceptional properties and a diverse range of oxidation states, which contribute to their superior specific capacitance compared to carbon-based materials [16, 17]. In particular, spinel-structured nickel cobaltite (NCO) stands out among various electrode candidates due to its cost-effectiveness and high theoretical specific capacitance, which arises from reversible and wealthier redox kinetics from Ni and Co ions [18, 19]. However, their inherently low electrical conductivity and tendency to agglomerate pose a significant challenge, adversely impacting rate performance and ultimately compromising cycle stability [20, 21]. Consequently, emerging advanced hierarchical architectural materials with synergistic properties and enhanced electrochemical performance are essential for SCs [1]. A defined mesoporous structure with appropriate surface area and high electrical conductivity is essential for material performance. Materials must offer abundant active sites for electrochemical reactions to enable rapid ion transport, thereby enhancing overall electrochemical efficiency [22]. Notably, morphological engineering and the introduction of foreign elements into the host matrix are recognized as highly effective approaches to optimizing the electrochemical performance of electrode materials [23]. It also serves as a strategic approach to fine-tune the electronic configuration, resulting in a substantial improvement in the electrode material's conductivity. This modification also increases the density of active sites, thereby enhancing electrochemical performance [24, 25]. It is also important to highlight that the presence of multiple metal cations within the electrode material results in synergistic effects, which significantly enhance both the specific capacitance and the energy storage capability [21]. Additionally, introducing metal cations into the host matrix enhances the structural stability of the electrode material, thereby mitigating volume fluctuations during electrochemical charge and discharge cycling. This stabilization ultimately optimizes the material's overall performance [23, 26, 27]. However, in extreme situations, excess metal cations in the host matrix can significantly reduce the density of electroactive sites or degrade the structure, thereby adversely affecting capacitance and cycling stability. Consequently, a systematic engineering approach is crucial for optimizing the integration of metal cations to enhance SC performance [28, 29].

Inspired by the above insights, NCO with a spinel structure was selected as the host matrix for synthesizing copper-incorporated electrodes for SC applications. Cu-incorporated NCO (CNCO) electrodes were produced using a hydrothermal process and subsequent heat treatment. The preparation involved varying the copper content of precursor materials to assess its impact on the structural and electrochemical characteristics of the

electrodes. This strategic incorporation of Cu significantly alters the electrode's morphology, enhancing electron transport and conductivity. The presence of multimetal cations enhances redox kinetics, resulting in more efficient electrochemical reactions. The porous framework facilitates charge and mass transport while accommodating volumetric changes during operation. The tailored CNCO material shows improvements in specific capacitance and rate performance, contributing to a high-performance BSH system with elevated specific capacitance, significant energy and power capabilities, and exceptional cyclic stability. The successful testing of the LED light in the tailored device highlights the material's enhanced charge-storage capability, making it a promising candidate for cutting-edge energy storage in real-world applications.

2 | Results and Discussion

The fabrication of CNCO nano/microarchitectures is illustrated in Scheme 1. This strategy involves a facile hydrothermal approach, followed by a calcination step. The process by which 3D microarchitectures develop from 1D nanostructures can be described by the hydrolysis of urea, resulting in CO_3^{2-} and OH^- in a water-based solution. Simultaneously, the metal ions engaged with those anions to form a metal-carbonate hydroxide. As a result, the hierarchical 3D nano/microarchitectures were produced through a single-step hydrothermal reaction. Initially, the primary particles of metal-carbonate hydroxide were generated through a nucleation process during the hydrothermal treatment. The metal-carbonate hydroxide nano/microarchitecture forms via the self-assembly of primary particles, thereby effectively reducing surface energy. Afterward, the synthesized metal-carbonate hydroxides were subjected to calcination, resulting in the formation of metal oxide (CNCO) nano/microarchitectures. During the calcination process, numerous pores can form as a result of the formation of nanoparticles in the 3D nano/microarchitectures. This occurs as the metal-carbonate hydroxide undergoes shrinkage, leading to a porous structure. Furthermore, during thermal annealing, gaseous substances like H_2O and CO_2 are released, resulting in the inner part of the CNCO nano/microarchitecture becoming porous.

The intricate morphologies of the CNCO products were examined by SEM to assess the effect of Cu dosage on the formation of 3D hierarchical nano- and microarchitectures. The findings are explored in Figures 1a-f and S1. It can be observed that significant variations in surface morphology are evident across the samples, highlighting that the morphology of the synthesized CNCO material is highly sensitive to copper concentration. As illustrated in Figure 1a, the synthesized CNCOA material exhibits a striking bilayer structure characterized by forming 3D microspheres reminiscent of urchins. These unique microspheres are intricately assembled from a network of elongated 1D nanoneedles that enhance their esthetic and functional properties. It is evident that the uppermost portions of the nanoneedles tend to cluster together, creating formations that resemble a densely packed bunch (Figure 1b). The basic structural units of the nanoneedles are arranged in a manner that radiates outward from a central core, resulting in a visually appealing and highly organized architecture, as shown in Figure 1c. The average diameter

SCHEME 1 | Synthetic pathway for the fabrication of hierarchical 3D CNCO nano/microarchitectures.

of these 3D urchin-like structures is approximately $4.3 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$. In contrast, the individual 1D nanoneedles possess a root diameter nearing $26.9 \pm 3.2 \text{ nm}$.

Furthermore, introducing Cu into the NCO host matrix significantly alters its morphological characteristics, leading to substantial morphological transformations. The introduction of copper led to a notable transformation of the surface morphology, resulting in a 3D coral-like nano/microarchitecture that contrasts with the earlier CNCOA urchin architecture. The findings demonstrate that Cu concentration significantly influences the surface morphologies of the CNCO nano/microstructures. The diameter of the material varies between 3.5 and 4.3 μm , which is characteristic of the coral-like CNCO nano/microarchitectures (Figures 1d and S1a,d). These unique architectures are characterized by their intricate 1D needle-like primary building blocks. As depicted in Figures 1e and S1b,e, these building blocks possess varying diameters, typically ranging from 21.2 to 29.9 nm. This size range is specifically associated with the distinct materials identified as CNCOB, CNCOC, and CNCOD (Figures 1f and S1c, f). Each of these materials plays a crucial role in contributing to the overall properties and functionalities of the 3D coral-like structure. Moreover, the 3D coral-like nano/microstructure, configured in a radial design, facilitates the formation of multiple “V-type” porous channels. The distinctive nano/microarchitecture establishes an open, porous framework that enables rapid ionic transport and diffusion into the superstructures. This configuration enhances the accessibility of active materials and optimizes the electrochemical reaction kinetics [30].

The morphology observed in the CNCOE sample synthesized with a copper concentration of 0.20 mmol is notable for its distinct structure. This structure is characterized by a collapsed coral-like form resulting from the aggregation and stacking of numerous nanoneedles. This intricate morphology is illustrated in Figure S1g–i, which provides visual evidence of the structural complexity and arrangement of the nanoneedles within the sample. This morphological alteration could significantly impair the material’s electrochemical performance. It is evident that the

amount of copper used in the synthesis process plays a crucial role in determining the morphology of the CNCO samples, underscoring the need for careful control of copper concentration to optimize the material’s properties.

To gain a clearer understanding of the morphology and crystallographic structure of the samples, both with and without Cu incorporation, we selected the CNCOA and CNCOD samples for TEM, HRTEM, and SAED analysis, as shown in Figure 1g–p. Upon close observation, it is evident that the interior of the microsphere exhibits a dark hue, sharply contrasting with its outer layer, which is characterized by a bright and vibrant appearance. The TEM image in Figure 1g elucidates the CNCOA, revealing its intricate micro/nanoscale urchin-like morphology characterized by a porous architecture. Furthermore, it can be obviously observed that the CNCOA nano/microarchitecture exhibits a surface primarily composed of nanoneedles, as illustrated in Figure 1h. Further analysis in Figure 1i demonstrates that these nanoneedles are aggregates of $\sim 9\text{--}12 \text{ nm}$ tiny spherical particles fused together, resulting in structures with an approximate diameter of $\sim 19\text{--}22 \text{ nm}$. Figure 1l–n presents TEM images at varying scale levels, revealing the effects of copper incorporation into the CNCOD nano/microarchitecture. Specifically, Figure 1l,m illustrates a well-defined coral-like nano/microarchitecture following Cu integration. The analysis shows that the porous architecture of the microspheres is characterized by a distinct white/black contrast, indicative of high porosity. The hierarchical porous framework comprises numerous nanoparticles, with sizes ranging from 10 to 13 nm. Furthermore, the diameters of the nanoneedles within this architecture are also consistent, falling within the $\sim 20\text{--}23 \text{ nm}$ range (Figure 1n). The formation of pores in the material results from the coral-like structure. These tiny cavities enhance the material’s capacitance to hold electrolytes by increasing contact with the CNCOD nano/microarchitecture. Furthermore, the pores shorten ion diffusion distances, promoting efficient ion movement during electrochemical reactions. This structural characteristic significantly enhances the material’s electrochemical performance during cycling, resulting in improved energy storage capabilities [31].

FIGURE 1 | SEM images at various magnifications of (a–c) CNCOA and (d–f) CNCOD nano/microarchitectural materials, TEM images recorded at innumerable amplification scales, HRTEM images, and SAED patterns: (g–k) CNCOA and (l–p) CNCOD nano/microarchitectural materials, (q) XRD patterns of CNCO nanomaterials, (r) Ni 2p, (s) Co 2p, (t) O 1s, (u) Cu 2p core level XPS spectra, and (v) BET isotherms graph (inset: BJH pore size distribution plots) of CNCOA and CNCOD nanomaterials.

HRTEM was used to confirm the structural integrity of the nano/microarchitectures of CNCOA and CNCOD, as depicted in Figure 1j,o. HRTEM images of the CNCOA and CNCOD nanomaterials clearly display distinct lattice fringes, a characteristic

indicative of their crystalline feature. The HRTEM image for both CNCOA and CNCOD nanomaterials, shown in Figure 1j,o, reveal lattice fringes measuring 0.46 nm. These dimensions can be attributed to the (111) crystal plane of the NiCo_2O_4

structure (PDF# 73–1702). The consistency in these lattice spacings indicates that incorporating copper into the structure does not alter the fundamental crystal architecture of the material. This stability is significant, as it implies that the desired properties of NiCo₂O₄ are preserved despite the modification, thereby enhancing the functionality of the nanomaterials for improved SC applications. In the meantime, the SAED patterns that reveal the diffraction spotty rings for the CNCOA and CNCOD nano/microarchitectures are portrayed in Figure 1k,p, respectively. These patterns provide valuable insight into the materials' crystallographic orientation and structural integrity, highlighting the unique characteristics that distinguish each architecture. The CNCOA and CNCOD nanomaterials exhibit a polycrystalline structure, as evidenced by the SAED patterns. The distinctive rings presented in the SAED patterns for both CNCOA and CNCOD nanomaterials align with the diffraction patterns characteristic of the cubic NiCo₂O₄ crystalline structure (PDF# 73–1702), confirming the crystalline phase of these nanomaterials. The absence of substantial Cu-based peaks indicates that copper is present in low concentrations within the materials, thereby reinforcing the successful incorporation of Cu into the NCO host matrix. This nano/microarchitecture framework enhances electron mobility and conductivity, ultimately improving electrochemical performance, as evidenced by the electrochemical analysis results. The HRTEM and SAED results are in strong agreement with the data from XRD analysis, as discussed below.

Furthermore, elemental composition analysis of the CNCO samples with varying Cu content was conducted to gain deeper insights into their characteristics, as shown in Figures S2 and S3. The elemental mapping of the CNCOA material, as illustrated in Figures S2ai-iv and S3ai-iv, revealed the presence of nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co), and oxygen (O). However, the EDS elemental mapping images of the other CNCOB, CNCOC, CNCOD, and CNCOE nano/microarchitectures illustrate the distribution of elements within the samples as portrayed in Figures S2b-ei-v and S3i-v. The mapping reveals the presence of four key components: nickel (Ni), copper (Cu), cobalt (Co), and oxygen (O). Notably, these elements exhibit a homogeneous distribution throughout the nano/microarchitectures, indicating an even integration of the Cu component. This finding confirms the successful incorporation of copper into the NCO host matrix, resulting in well-defined Cu-containing CNCO formations. Such uniformity in elemental distribution is crucial for ensuring the stability and performance of the materials in SC applications.

The crystal structure and phase characteristics of the synthesized CNCO nanomaterials were determined using XRD analysis at varying levels of copper incorporation (Figure 1q). The incorporation of the Cu component into the crystal lattice of the host material has been further analyzed. XRD data reveal distinct diffraction peaks, confirming that all synthesized samples exhibit a crystalline structure. The observed diffraction peaks at 18.9°, 31.1°, 36.7°, 38.4°, 44.6°, 55.4°, 59.1°, 64.9°, and 77.0° correspond to the Miller indices (111), (220), (311), (222), (400), (422), (511), (440), and (533), respectively. The observed peaks align well with the cubic spinel structure characteristic of NiCo₂O₄, as confirmed by the reference pattern (PDF# 73–1702). Notably, the cubic structure remains stable upon the incorporation of Cu species, as evidenced by the absence of significant peaks associated with copper oxide or other contaminant phases. This suggests that the

Cu species are effectively integrated into the NiCo₂O₄ lattice without disrupting its inherent crystal structure. The presence of copper species in the NiCo₂O₄ crystal lattice can be attributed to the similarity in ionic radius between Cu²⁺ (0.72 Å) and Ni²⁺ (0.69 Å) [32]. This close resemblance facilitates the easy incorporation of Cu species into the lattice structure, suggesting that copper likely exists in ionic form within the material. This observation indicates that a single phase has been retained across all compositions. This implies successful Cu incorporation without substantial disruption to the host material's crystal structure, thereby validating the synthesis approach's efficacy in preserving the integrity of the crystal-line framework. Besides, the diffraction peak intensities increase slightly, while the peak width decreases slightly as the Cu concentration increases. The crystallite sizes of all synthesized materials were quantified using Scherrer's equation, which increased from 7.6 to 9.2 nm. These results indicate that the incorporation of Cu into the lattice significantly enhances the material's crystallinity [26, 33, 34]. The effective integration of copper introduces lattice distortions and generates defect sites that serve as supplementary catalytic centers. These structural modifications are pivotal for enhancing electronic conductivity and increasing the number of available electroactive sites, both of which are crucial for optimizing SC performance [26, 35].

The XPS technique was used to analyze the elemental composition and examine the electronic structure of the CNCOA and CNCOD nanomaterials. The XPS survey spectra (Figure S4a) confirm the presence of nickel (Ni), copper (Cu), cobalt (Co), and oxygen (O), indicating that the chemical composition is consistent with that of the samples. Notably, no additional peaks corresponding to other elements were observed, affirming the purity of the constituent elements analyzed. The Ni 2p spectra, illustrated in Figure 1r, reveal a deconvolution into six distinct peaks. The peaks observed at 873.4 and 871.8 eV correspond to the Ni 2p_{1/2} transitions of Ni²⁺ and Ni³⁺, respectively. Similarly, the peaks at 853.9 and 855.5 eV correspond to the Ni 2p_{3/2} states of Ni²⁺ and Ni³⁺. Additionally, the remaining peaks at 861.2 and 879.5 eV are attributed to shake-up satellite features [36, 37]. The high-resolution Co 2p spectra (Figure 1s) expose distinct peaks at 796.8 and 794.8 eV corresponding to Co 2p_{1/2} and 781.7 and 779.8 eV corresponding to Co 2p_{3/2}. These peaks are indicative of the presence of Co²⁺ and Co³⁺ oxidation states, respectively. Additionally, two shake-up satellite peaks are observed at 803.3 eV (Co 2p_{1/2}) and 787.0 eV (Co 2p_{3/2}) [37, 38]. The XPS spectra for the O 1s region are presented in Figure 1t. The core-level spectra disclose three predominant sub-peaks, denoted as O_A, O_B, and O_C. The O_A peak at 529.3 eV indicates oxygen atoms incorporated into metal–oxygen (M–O) bonds. In contrast, the O_B peak, which appears at 531.1 eV, suggests the existence of defect sites within the material that are characterized by a lower coordination of oxygen atoms. In regions with oxygen deficiency, the OH[−] groups are bonded to metal ions, which helps preserve charge balance. The presence of these OH[−] groups is linked to the number of oxygen vacancies, which serve as collaring centers for charge carriers. These defect sites can significantly affect the material's electronic properties and ultimately enhance its catalytic activity [39]. Finally, the O_C peak observed at 533.1 eV indicates oxygen species that are chemically or physically adsorbed on the surface [40, 41]. The XPS data reveal that the oxygen defect concentration for CNCOD material is 45.1%, surpassing the CNCOA level at 43.6%. This observation indicates that the inclusion of copper within the host matrix facilitates the formation of

oxygen vacancies. These enhanced oxygen defects are expected to improve intrinsic conductivity and accelerate the kinetics of electrochemical redox reactions, thereby enhancing performance in SC applications [39, 42, 43]. Furthermore, the high-resolution Cu 2p XPS spectrum is presented in Figure 1u. The Cu 2p_{3/2} and Cu 2p_{1/2} peaks are observed at 933.9 eV and 953.2 eV, respectively, accompanied by two prominent satellite peaks. This observation corroborates the presence of Cu element as Cu²⁺ ions within the sample [42].

The metal compositions of the CNCO samples were determined through inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES) analysis. The mole ratio of Ni/Cu/Co was found to be 1.001:0.00:1.999, 0.990:0.011:1.999, 0.970:0.029:2.001, 0.948:0.051:2.001, and 0.931:0.069:2.000 for CNCOA, CNCOB, CNCOC, CNCOD, and CNCOE, respectively. Furthermore, it is noted that the Ni concentration in CNCO materials diminishes from CNCOA to CNCOE, while the Cu concentration exhibits a corresponding increase. Thus, the materials demonstrate strong alignment with the intended nominal values established in the initial solution for CNCO nano/microarchitecture materials.

The specific surface area (SSA) and porosity characteristics of the CNCO nanomaterials were assessed through BET and BJH analysis utilizing N₂ adsorption isotherms. The mesoporous characteristics of the CNCO nano/micromaterials are substantiated by the presence of an H3-model hysteresis loop in conjunction with a type IV adsorption isotherm, shown in Figures 1v and S4b. The mesoporous structure of the synthesized materials significantly enhances electrochemical performance by facilitating the diffusion of the electrolyte to the electrode's active sites. It also promotes rapid electron and ion transport across the electrode/electrolyte interface, thereby optimizing overall electrochemical kinetics [44]. The SSA determined by the BET method for the nanomaterials CNCOA, CNCOB, CNCOC, CNCOD, and CNCOE are measured at 129.2, 80.5, 86.2, 97.1, and 70.9 m²/g, respectively.

The SSA of the copper-incorporated CNCO nanoarchitectures is lower than that of the host matrix. This reduction can be attributed to the occlusion of pores within the coral-like nanoarchitectures. This observation is further supported by the shape of the hysteresis loop, which confirms the successful incorporation of copper into the host matrix [45]. The findings suggest that optimal levels of Cu incorporation enhance the SSA of the nanoarchitectures by effectively reducing the nanoneedle diameter. However, excessive Cu incorporation results in a reduction of the SSA, as evidenced by the morphological changes observed in the SEM images. Furthermore, the corresponding porous features were derived from the isotherm using the Barrett–Joyner–Halenda (BJH) method, as illustrated in Figures inset of 1v and S4c. The total pore volumes for CNCOA, CNCOB, CNCOC, CNCOD, and CNCOE were measured at 0.326, 0.244, 0.308, 0.298, and 0.282 cm³/g, respectively. These pore volumes enhance the transport dynamics of electrolyte ions, facilitating their migration within the material. Furthermore, the average pore diameters for CNCOA, CNCOB, CNCOC, CNCOD, and CNCOE are found to be 5.61, 7.32, 7.32, 6.44, and 33.32 nm, respectively. The electrode's appropriate surface area and porosity significantly minimize ion diffusion pathways, thereby augmenting its electrochemical energy storage performance. Thus, the CNCOD nanomaterial exhibited an optimal balance of surface area and porosity, facilitating enhanced interaction between the electrode and the electrolyte. This structural advantage significantly improved the diffusion kinetics of electrolyte ions, underscoring the positive impact of an appropriately selected copper concentration within the host matrix [44, 46].

A series of electrochemical investigations, including CV, GCD, and EIS, was conducted to evaluate the electrochemical performance of CNCO electrode materials. The experiments used a three-electrode setup in a 6 M KOH electrolyte, as illustrated in Figures 2 and S5–S8. The comparative analysis of the CVs for electrodes CNCOA, CNCOB, CNCOC, CNCOD, and CNCOE was conducted at a scan rate of 30 mV/s. This evaluation

FIGURE 2 | (a) Comparative analysis of GCD profiles at 1 A/g of CNCO electrode materials, (b) assessment of specific capacitance evaluated at 1 A/g of CNCO electrode materials, (c and d) CVs and GCD profiles at different sweep rates and current densities of CNCOD electrode, and (e) assessing the specific capacitance of CNCOD as a function of varying current densities.

specifically emphasizes optimizing Cu incorporation levels within each electrode formulation. The results of this analysis are illustrated in Figure S5a, where variations in electrochemical performance are observed associated with different copper concentrations. When comparing electrode materials, it is evident that Cu-incorporated electrode materials exhibit a significantly higher charge storage capacity than their host counterparts. This enhancement can be attributed to the unique electronic and structural properties introduced by copper incorporation, which optimize the overall performance and efficiency of the electrode material for energy storage applications. Notably, the CV analysis of the CNCOD electrode reveals a significantly larger integrated area and a more pronounced current-density peak than those of the other CNCO electrodes, suggesting it has the highest discharge capacitance among the group. The superior electrochemical performance of the CNCOD electrode can be attributed to its optimal copper content, which mitigates excessive aggregation and maintains an adequate density of active sites for ion transport, thereby ensuring a high specific capacitance [26]. The synergistic interplay between Cu and the NCO host matrix significantly enhances electrochemical performance, positioning this combination as a highly promising candidate for energy storage applications. In addition, incorporating Cu into the NCO host counterpart markedly enhances its overall conductivity, making it a more reactive component within the material. Moreover, all the electrode materials demonstrated noticeable Faradaic redox behavior, characterized by distinct redox peaks and nonrectangular current responses in CVs. These observations indicate typical battery-like capacitive properties, attributed to the reversible redox reactions occurring during the conversions of X–O/X–O–OH (where X includes Ni, Cu, and Co) [37, 47].

The GCD profiles of the synthesized CNCO electrodes with varying Cu contents are shown in Figure 2a at 1 A/g. The dominant capacitive characteristics of the electrodes, akin to those of a battery, are evidenced by the nonlinear discharge profiles, which exhibit a plateau. The observed features arise from the inherent Faradaic reactions associated with battery-type processes, which are linked to the multivalence interconversions of various chemical species. These reactions involve the transfer of electrons and ions, enabling the reversible oxidation and reduction of different oxidation states [48]. The CNCOD electrode exhibited a longer discharge duration, indicating its enhanced charge storage capacity compared to other CNCO electrodes. This observation is consistent with the findings derived from the CV measurements. Notably, the CNCOD electrode exhibits the highest specific capacitance, with a substantial value of 1301 F/g, measured at 1 A/g. In contrast, the other electrodes, including CNCOA, CNCOB, CNCOE, and CNCOF electrodes, exhibit inferior specific capacities, with values of 519, 723, 978, and 604 F/g, respectively (Figure 2b), under the same test conditions. The enhanced electrochemical performance of the CNCOD electrode can be attributed to its optimal copper content, which reduces the propensity for excessive particle aggregation. This balance

maintains a sufficient density of active sites, facilitating efficient ion transport and contributing to a high specific capacitance [26].

To elucidate the fundamental mechanisms underlying the improved energy storage performance, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is used to analyze the key attributes of SC electrode materials and characterize the kinetics of electrolyte ion transport. Figure S5b, c illustrates the Nyquist plot corresponding to the EIS data of the electrodes based on the CNCO electrodes. In the high-frequency domain of EIS spectra, the intersection with the real axis represents the solution resistance (R_s). This encompasses the intrinsic resistance of the materials, contact resistance, and the resistance presented by the electrolyte [49]. The diameter of the semicircular arc in the high-to-medium frequency region of the Z axis corresponds to the sum of the charge transfer resistance and the ohmic resistance, providing a rough estimate of the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) at the electrolyte interface [50]. The slope along the imaginary impedance axis in the low-frequency domain corresponds to the Warburg resistance, attributed to ion diffusion [51]. The estimated R_s for the CNCOA, CNCOB, CNCOE, CNCOD, and CNCOF electrodes are 1.02, 0.84, 0.78, 0.66, and 0.92 Ω , respectively. Among these, CNCOD showed the lowest R_s , which is consistent with the highest electrochemical properties observed in the CV and GCD results. This suggests effective ionic conductivity in the electrolyte and minimal resistance at the interface between the electrode and electrolyte. The impedance analysis indicates an imperfect semicircle, with R_{ct} values determined to be 0.81, 0.64, 0.58, 0.51, and 0.73 Ω for the CNCOA, CNCOB, CNCOE, CNCOD, and CNCOF electrodes, respectively. The findings indicate that optimal integration of copper into the CNCOD electrode significantly enhances its charge and ion-transfer capabilities. Additionally, the reduced resistance represents the improved electron conductivity within the electrode, contributing to the superior electrochemical performance observed in the optimized Cu-incorporated formulation. In the low-frequency area, the observed linear segment is indicative of the diffusion process of electroactive species. A steeper slope of the CNCOD electrode in this segment reflects a lower diffusion resistance than other CNCOD electrodes. The optimized incorporation of copper into the CNCOD electrode results in a significantly steeper slope, highlighting an improved ionic diffusion within the electrode material. The strategic integration of foreign species into the host matrix can enhance conductivity and facilitate rapid ion/electron transfer [52]. Notably, the CNCOD electrode exhibits lower impedance values than other CNCO electrodes, indicating its superior electrochemical activity. The increased specific capacitance upon adding Cu suggests that the electrochemical properties can be fine-tuned, making it a promising material for future energy storage applications [32]. The result relies on the optimal amount of Cu incorporation, which enhances the electron conductivity and charge kinetics of CNCO electrodes. Overall, chemical ion diffusion depends on electronic conductivity and electrolyte ion diffusion. Increasing Cu could boost electron mobility but reduce the ion mobility. Thus, the best electrochemical performance strikes a balance between electron mobility and ion diffusion [50].

Figures 2c and S6 present the CVs of the CNCO electrodes, allowing for a clear differentiation of SC behavior based on the area beneath the CVs recorded at varied scan rates ranging from 5 to

50 mV/s. All CVs exhibited a stable shape, even at elevated scan rates, demonstrating outstanding redox reversibility and robust rate performance [53]. At elevated sweeping speeds, the current density can escalate, leading to a nonuniform distribution of ions. This phenomenon contributes to a further reduction in capacitance. The voltammograms exhibit prominent redox peaks, indicating that the SC electrodes developed from these materials primarily engage in battery-type faradaic processes for storing and releasing electrical charges. The observed shift in the oxidation and reduction peaks can be attributed to the significant polarization of the electrode material, a phenomenon resulting from the elevated scan rate.

To clarify the charge storage mechanism and the kinetics of reactions within the CNCOA and CNCOD electrodes at various scan rates (5–50 mV/s), the data were systematically calculated and analyzed according to the principles of the power law: $i = av^b$ [26, 47]. In this context, the variables a and b denote adjustable parameters, while v represents the applied scan rate. The b -value was determined from the slope of the $\log(i)$ versus $\log(v)$ plot, offering valuable insights into the underlying charge-storage mechanism. The b value of 0.5 typically indicates that the process is primarily governed by diffusion, whereas the value of 1 signifies a process controlled by surface capacitive effects. The b -values for CNCOA and CNCOD are calculated to be 0.74 and 0.78, and 0.48 and 0.54, respectively (Figure S7a,d). The b -value of Cu incorporated CNCOD is lower than that of CNCOA, indicating a further decrease in b -value and suggesting an augmented contribution from diffusion-controlled processes. The findings indicate that incorporating copper significantly augments surface control mechanisms and, crucially, enhances the kinetic efficiency of the Faradaic reaction by optimizing pathways for ion diffusion [8].

The contributions of capacitance control versus diffusion control to overall charge storage in CNCOA and CNCOD electrodes can be assessed using Dunn's method: $i = k_1v + k_2v^{1/2}$ [43, 54, 55]. In this context, i denotes the response current, while k_1v and $k_2v^{1/2}$ correspond to the processes governed by capacitance and diffusion, respectively. The surface capacitance contribution ratios of the CNCOA electrode at different scan rates of 5, 10, 20, 30, and 50 mV/s are 73, 74, 76, 79, and 84% respectively (Figure S7b,c). As scan rates increase from low to high, ion reactions become increasingly incomplete due to insufficient diffusion within the reduced time frame. As a result, the influence of diffusion control at the electrode decreases, while the contribution from capacitive control increases, ultimately reaching its peak. Compared to the NCOA electrode, the NCO electrode shows a significant reduction in surface capacitance contributions, with decreases of 57, 59, 61, 66, and 71%, at scan rates of 5, 10, 20, 30, and 50 mV/s, respectively (Figure S7e,f). The findings suggest that incorporating copper into the host NCO matrix significantly enhances diffusion-controlled processes associated with the formation of oxygen vacancies. This enhancement is attributed to the increased electrical conductivity observed in the Cu introduced CNCOD electrode compared to the CNCOA electrode. Consequently, the CNCOD electrode demonstrates improved electrolyte-ion storage capacity, coupled with exceptional rate performance [8].

Furthermore, the GCD test is a reliable method for evaluating electrochemical capacitance, confirming the capacitive properties of

CNCO electrodes with varying Cu contents at different current densities, as presented in Figures 2d and S8. The plateaus observed in the GCD profile of electrode materials suggest nonlinear charging and discharging profiles that are roughly equivalent in duration. This phenomenon is indicative of battery-like behavior primarily influenced by Faradaic reactions. The nonlinear GCD profiles reflect the deviations from ideal SC behavior. As the current density increases, the time required to charge and discharge the energy storage system decreases. This is primarily attributed to the mechanisms involved in surface charge storage, which allow for faster charge transfer at the interface between the electrode and the electrolyte. However, at elevated current densities, ion transport from the electrolyte to the electrode becomes restricted, primarily at the electrode surface. This limitation in ion transport reduces the system's specific capacitance, as the total charge that can be stored per unit mass of the electrode material is reduced. Consequently, while higher currents can enhance the speed of energy delivery, they also compromise the overall capacitance performance due to these transport limitations [26]. The GCD profiles maintain well-defined, symmetric shapes with distinct voltage plateaus even at high current density. This behavior suggests that the CNCO electrodes exhibit significant reversibility and outstanding charge storage capacity across the GCD cycles [56]. There is no discernible IR drop even at 20 A/g, suggesting that the I–V response of the CNCOD electrode is rapid and efficient [20].

Figures 2e and S9 provide a detailed comparative analysis of the performance metrics of CNCO electrodes under different applied current densities. The specific capacitance exhibits a progressive diminution as the current density increases, which can be attributed to the inadequate redox reactions that occur within the constrained time intervals [48]. Whereas electrolyte ions can fully penetrate the surface of the active material, enabling efficient diffusion at lower current densities. This enhances the utilization of internal active sites and pores for charge storage, leading to higher capacitance. The CNCOD electrode stands out significantly with a remarkable specific capacitance of 1057 F/g when evaluated at 20 A/g. This impressive performance underscores its potential effectiveness in energy storage applications. In comparison, the other electrodes, specifically, CNCOA, CNCOB, CNCOE, and CNCOF, show considerably lower specific capacitances. The CNCOA electrode exhibits a specific capacitance of only 319 F/g, while CNCOB achieves a capacitance of 506 F/g. The performance of CNCOE is somewhat better at 725 F/g, yet it still falls short of CNCOD's capabilities. Finally, the CNCOF electrode shows a specific capacitance of 335 F/g. These results highlight the superior electrochemical performance of the CNCOD electrode relative to its counterparts. Furthermore, the CNCOD electrode exhibits an impressive rate capability of 81.3%. In contrast, the performance of the other CNCO variants, namely CNCOA, CNCOB, CNCOE, and CNCOF, falls significantly short, with corresponding rates of 61.5, 69.9, 74.1, and 55.5%, respectively, under 20 A/g. The capacitance and rate performance of CNCO electrodes improve with Cu incorporation; however, care must be taken to control the amount, as excess Cu can decrease electrochemical performance [57, 58]. It highlights the need for a suitable level of Cu incorporation to balance interfacial charge transfer and structural integrity, as any imbalance leads to compensatory effects [50, 59]. Thus, the superior electrochemical performance and enhanced rate capability of the CNCOD electrode can be ascribed to the optimal amount of Cu incorporation into the host material. This optimization mitigates material aggregation,

maintains an ideal density of active sites for ion transport, and ultimately supports elevated SC performance [26].

To investigate the effect of Cu-ion incorporation on the electronic structures of CNCO nanomaterials, density functional theory (DFT) was used. The initial structural relaxation for bulk and (311) facet was performed using PBE (Perdew–Burke–Erenzerhof) exchange–correlation functional, as represented in Figure 3. In order to assess the effect of Cu-ion incorporation on the electronic structure of the CNCO, the computed projected density of states (PDOS) was used for CNCOA and CNCOD (Figures 4a,b). It can be observed that a significantly dominant population of Co-d-band states near the Fermi level (−2.0 to 0.0 eV) in CNCOA. In the case of CNCOD, we observed a marginal change in total Co-d-band occupancy; however, a significant change in Ni-d-band population was noted near the Fermi level. Specifically, a marginal shift in the Ni-d-band very close to the Fermi level, ~ -0.5 to 0.0 eV in the Cu-ion incorporation system (as highlighted in the green region of Figure 4a, b). The subtle shift in the Ni-d-band near the Fermi level suggests that the incorporation of Cu-ions may facilitate a reduction in the band gap of host NCO nanomaterials.

Further, to quantitatively understand the effect of Cu-ion incorporation, the Bader charge analysis using the PBE functional was performed. We computed average net atomic charges for Co, Ni, and O in CNCOA and CNCOD. The average net atomic charges for cobalt show insignificant changes in CNCOA (1.445 e) and CNCOD (1.447 e) systems. However, nickel exhibits two different sets of atomic charges in CNCOD (1.215 and 1.229 e) compared to CNCOA (1.218 e). The incorporation of Cu ions into the NCO host matrix introduces defects in the crystal lattice, thereby

improving the electrocatalytic activity of the electrode material. However, it leads to the generation of under coordinated transition metal and oxygen sites that can be stabilized via adsorbed OH^- species or water molecules on the surface.

Therefore, to access the interaction between adsorbed water molecules and the most stable facet (311) of CNCOD, the computed projected DOS with and without water molecules (Figure 4c–e). In the case of a water adsorbed system, a significant overlap between the O-p-band of water molecules and transition metal (TM)-d-band near the Fermi level (−2.0 to 0.0 eV) can be noticed, indicating a strong bonding interaction between water molecules and metal surface (Figure 4c–e). To gain a comprehensive understanding of the interaction of water molecules with the most exposed surface (311) of CNCOD, charge density difference (CDD) analysis was performed (Figure 4f). A remarkable interaction can be observed between the TM-d-orbital shaped charge-depleted surface (blue color isosurface) on metal and the O-p-orbital shaped charged-rich surface (yellow color isosurface) (Figure 4f). The electronic structure analysis suggests that the adsorbed water molecules help to stabilize the under coordinated metal sites during the electrocatalytic process.

The viability of the CNCOD nanomaterial in a dual-electrode system was investigated by constructing a BSH using activated carbon (AC) and CNCOD as the negative and positive electrodes, respectively. The electrochemical properties of the BSH are illustrated in Figures 5, 6, and S10. Based on the observed distinct electrochemical responses, it can be anticipated that the full cell will encompass the complete potential range of the individual electrodes. To uphold charge neutrality, the mass of the negative

FIGURE 3 | Structural screenshots for (a) CNCOA, (b) CNCOD, (c) side-view of the most abundant facet (311) of CNCOD, (d) top-view of (311) of CNCOD, and (e) top-view to represent water adsorption at the (311) facet of CNCOD using the PBE functional.

FIGURE 4 | Projected density of states (PDOS) for (a) bulk NCO, (d) CNCOD, (c) (311) facet of CNCOD, (d) (311) facet of CNCOD with H₂O adsorbed on the surface, (e) close-up view to represent O-p-bands of H₂O molecule (shown in cyan color), and (f) graphical representation of charge density difference (CDD) plot for water adsorbed (311) facet of CNCOD using PBE functional with isosurface value 0.0084 (the yellow-colored isosurface represents the charge gained region, and blue-colored isosurface shows the charge depleted region; black-colored spheres highlight some of the TM-d-orbital and O-p-orbital interaction at the surface).

electrode was determined by applying the mass balance equation to both electrodes. Figure S10a illustrates the CVs for both the AC and CNCOD electrodes at a scan rate of 50 mV/s. The AC electrode operates effectively within a potential range of -1 to 0 V, while the CNCOD electrode functions optimally from 0 to 0.5 V. Consequently, the overall operational voltage of the assembled BSH using the configuration CNCOD//AC can be extended to a maximum of 1.5 V. The CVs of the AC electrode, exhibiting a potential window from -1 to 0 V, are illustrated in Figure S10b. The CVs of the BSH were recorded over a voltage range of 1.0 – 1.5 V, using a scan rate of 50 mV/s. As depicted in Figure S10c, the resulting CVs exhibited remarkable stability over the voltage range, with no significant signs of polarization. This behavior indicates that the electrochemical processes in the

BSH are efficient and well-managed within the tested voltage range. Notably, 1.5 V is identified as the optimal operating voltage for the assembled BSH, highlighting its effectiveness in energy storage applications. The GCD profiles were also recorded at a current density of 5 A/g across various voltage windows, as shown in Figure S10d. A clear observation from these profiles is their quasi-symmetric nature, indicating that the discharge profiles closely mirror the charge segments throughout the testing range. This symmetry persists even when the voltage window is extended to 1.5 V, highlighting the system's high Coulombic efficiency. Based on these findings, the optimal operating voltage for the BSH tested in this work is 1.5 V, which maximizes its performance and efficiency during cycling. The total voltage range encompasses the sum of both the AC and CNCOD electrodes.

The CVs for the CNCOD//AC BSH at varying scan rates exhibit a notable deviation from the expected rectangular profile typically associated with ideal capacitive behavior. This deviation can primarily be attributed to the complex redox reactions occurring within the positive material, as illustrated in Figure 5a. As the scan rate increases, the CVs maintain a consistent shape, an encouraging indicator of the device's high reversibility and stability throughout the electrochemical processes. This stability suggests that the BSH's performance characteristics are reliable across different operational speeds. The GCD profiles of the BSH at various

current densities are depicted in Figure 5b. The BSH operates effectively over a voltage range of 0–1.5 V, exhibiting nonlinear behavior attributed to the underlying redox reactions during charge and discharge cycles. Notably, even as current densities increase, the overall shape of the GCDs remains consistent, indicating the stability of the BSH's performance under varying load conditions. This stability suggests that the BSH exhibits excellent rate performance, facilitating rapid electron and ion transfer within the system. Such efficient kinetics are crucial for applications that require rapid energy delivery and high-power output.

FIGURE 5 | The electrochemical performance assessment of the BSH system (CNCOD//AC): (a) CVs at different scan speeds, (b) GCD profiles at various current densities, (c) the graph of the specific capacitance characteristics across varying current densities, (d) the Ragone plot in the context of varying current densities and its correlation with prior research findings, (e) cyclic stability and Coulombic efficiency of the BSH system, and the Nyquist impedance spectra for the BSH of (f) prior to cycling and (g) subsequent to cycling.

Additionally, the relationship between the discharging specific capacitance and current density is shown in Figure 5c. Remarkably, the BSH exhibits a specific capacitance of 196 F/g when tested at 1 A/g. Even at a higher current density of 20 A/g, it retains a commendable specific capacitance of 119 F/g. This performance indicates a capacitance retention rate of 60.4%, highlighting the impressive rate capability of this BSH system. Such characteristics suggest that the BSH is efficient at lower current levels and maintains substantial energy storage performance during rapid discharge. Figure 5d presents Ragone plots illustrating the energy and power density characteristics of the CNCOD//AC BSH system with various devices. This comparison highlights the performance of the BSH developed in this study against other BSHs reported in the literature. Notably, the CNCOD//AC BSH demonstrates an impressive energy density of 61.36 Wh/kg when operating at a power density of 1.18 kW/kg. This remarkable performance is further underscored by the BSH's ability to maintain an energy density of 37.04 Wh/kg even under a higher power density of 16.64 kW/kg. Furthermore, the energy density exhibited by this BSH surpassed that of various other constructed BSHs, including NCO-Ar/H₂-10//AC (48.6 Wh/kg at 799.6 W/kg) [20], Co-NiMoO₄//AC (16.2 Wh/kg at 725.0 W/kg) [22], Al_{1.0}-NiCo₂O₄//AC (58.3 Wh/kg at 800.3 W/kg) [24], SrCo_{0.95}Cr_{0.05}O_{3-δ}@CC//PPy@CC (44.9 Wh/kg at 902.0 W/kg) [28], Co-doped W₁₈O₄₉/CC//AC/CC (35.0 Wh/kg at 801.0 W/kg) [43], CFS-0.06//AC (31.8 Wh/kg at 800 W/kg) [52], Ni-Co-Cu Oxide//AC (42.1 Wh/kg at 374.9 W/kg) [54], F-ZnWO₄₋₂//RuO₂-ZnO (37.4 Wh/kg at 831.4 W/kg) [55], and Cu-Co₃O₄@F-CNTs//AC (30.8 Wh/kg at 754.5 W/kg) [60].

The long-term cycling stability of the BSH system is critically assessed at a current density of 10 A/g over 30 000 cycles, serving as a key performance metric. The cyclic retention and Coulombic efficiency of the BSH are displayed in Figure 5e. Remarkably, the BSH demonstrates an impressive retention of 93.2% of its initial capacitance after 30,000 GCD cycles. This significant behavior highlights the exceptional cyclic stability of the BSH, indicating that it maintains its performance across repeated GCD cycles. Besides, the Coulombic efficiency consistently hovers around 99.8% during the process, indicating excellent reversibility. The inset in Figure 5e displays the initial and final five cycles of GCD performance during the cyclic stability assessment. This highlights the impressive cyclic stability of the BSH system, demonstrating consistent performance throughout the test. Thus, the remarkable electrochemical stability of the materials can be ascribed to the optimal incorporation of Cu into the host matrix and the structural stability of the 3D nano/microarchitecture.

The exceptional cycling stability of the BSH system is further validated by the EIS results obtained before and after the stability test, as portrayed in the Figure 5f,g. The observed R_s values are 0.72 and 0.89 Ω. Additionally, the R_{ct} associated with the electrochemical process is recorded as 1.45 Ω prior to the cycling test and 1.63 Ω following the test, indicating a nominal change in resistance characteristics after cycling. The minimal increase in the R_{ct} values following 30,000 continuous charge/discharge cycles indicates the remarkable durability of the assembled BSH. Moreover, the slope of the linear region in the low-frequency domain was nearly consistent, indicating excellent electrochemical stability. The CNCOD material is increasingly recognized as a superior candidate for the positive electrode in BSHs. This is

attributed to the synergistic interactions between the copper component and the NCO host material, coupled with the strategic incorporation of foreign elements into the host matrix. Furthermore, its unique surface-oriented 3D phenomena enhance its electrochemical performance.

To gain a better understanding of the CNCOD nano/microarchitecture electrode material, we conducted post-characterization analysis to examine its physicochemical properties. The findings from this analysis are presented in Figure S11. The XRD patterns of the CNCOD electrode, both in its standard pattern and following stability tests, are presented in Figure S11a. The analysis of these XRD patterns reveals no notable alteration in the spinel crystal structure, as evidenced by the consistency of the diffraction peaks with the standard pattern after conducting the stability tests. This observation is further corroborated by PDF# 73-1702, which confirms the stability of the crystalline structure throughout the testing period. Furthermore, SEM analysis was used to provide a detailed examination of the morphology of the CNCOD electrode material after completion of the stability tests, as shown in Figure S11b–d. Remarkably, the morphology of the electrode material continues to exhibit its hierarchical 3D coral-like nano/microarchitecture, even after enduring extensive cycling over a prolonged duration. This structural durability indicates that the material's integrity has been preserved, highlighting its stability throughout the rigorous testing period. Additionally, the stability test results suggest that, despite prolonged exposure to cycling conditions, the material remains electrochemically active. The findings presented above substantiate that the CNCOD electrode material exhibits outstanding electrochemical performance, with remarkable durability and enhanced operational efficiency. This combination of structural integrity and sustained electrochemical activity underscores the material's robustness and suitability for practical use.

The viability of the SC device for real-time applications was assessed by fabricating BSH devices with CNCOD as the positive electrode and AC as the negative electrode. Figure 6a shows a photographic image of the resulting BSH devices, which consist of two-coin cells connected in series. The inset in Figure 6a illustrates a single coin cell for reference. When BSH devices are configured in series, the overall voltage output of the system is aggregated by the sum of the voltage of each cell. This results in a linear increase in voltage proportional to the number of BSH cells in series, effectively multiplying the system's voltage potential with each added unit. As shown in Figure 6b, the single BSH system outputs a voltage of 1.50 V, indicating its basic operational capabilities. However, when two BSH devices are linked in series, the system can achieve a remarkable voltage range of up to 3.18 V (Figure 6c). This capability not only enhances the device's overall electrochemical performance but also significantly broadens its potential applications. Their unique design and performance characteristics position them as a promising option in the evolving landscape of energy storage technologies. The exceptional cycling stability of the HSC enables consistent, reliable performance over extended periods, making it an optimal power source for electronic applications. The setup involves an open circuit in which a BSH is charged for approximately 80 s while connected to inactive light-emitting diode (LED) goggles, as depicted in Figures 6d,f. Post-charge, these BSH devices were utilized to power the LEDs, producing a display pattern reading 'DGU'. The accompanying digital image captures the real-time

FIGURE 6 | Digital photographic images of the real-time implementation of the CNCOD//AC BSH systems: (a) two BSH cells connected in series (inset for the as-fabricated individual BSH cells), the output voltage of the charged BSH cells measured by a digital multimeter for (b) the single cell and (c) the two serially connected cells, commercial LEDs organized in the “DGU” pattern, before and after their connection to the BSHs, (d,e) a green coloration and (f,g) a pink coloration.

performance of the BSH devices in their coin-cell arrangement, successfully illuminating the green and pink LEDs during operation, as shown in Figure 6e,g. Conspicuously, the LED indicators are efficiently driven by this BSH system, demonstrating the commercial viability of the device.

3 | Conclusions

In summary, cost-effective Cu-incorporated hierarchical 3D binary spinel NiCo_2O_4 (CNCO) nano/microarchitecture has been successfully prepared using a two-step approach involving hydrothermal and heat treatment. The effect of varying copper content on the nano/microstructural characteristics and electrochemical performance of the electrode material was investigated. The synergistic interactions within the CNCO electrode material led to alterations in its electronic structure, which consequently generated intrinsic porosities. Moreover, simulation results derived from DFT confirm that the CNCOD electrode material exhibits superior catalytic activity, alongside optimal OH^- adsorption. Among the electrodes evaluated, the CNCOD electrode demonstrated superior electrochemical performance, achieving a remarkable specific capacitance of 1301 F/g when tested at 1 A/g. The exceptional performance can

be attributed to the synergistic interactions among the optimal Cu content, the NCO host matrix, and mesoporous structure with an appropriate SSA, which together enhance the availability of redox-active sites for ions. This design facilitates rapid ion traversal, resulting in improved electronic conductivity. In addition, the integrated CNCOD//AC BSH system demonstrates impressive performance metrics, achieving an energy density of 61.36 Wh/kg and a power density of 16.64 kW/kg, as well as remarkable cycling stability (93.2% over 30,000 charge–discharge cycles). Hence, the engineering of multimetal oxides featuring innovative nano/microarchitectures presents a promising strategy for advancing the performance of electrode materials in energy storage applications.

4 | Experimental Section

4.1 | Preparation of Cu Incorporated NiCo_2O_4 (CNCO) Nanomaterials

All chemicals utilized in this study were of analytical grade and used without any additional purification processes. A facile hydrothermal approach was used to produce a range of Cu-incorporated NiCo_2O_4 nanomaterials, which were subsequently subjected to

calcination. Initially, a precursor solution was prepared by weighing out x mmol of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $4-x$ mmol of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 8 mmol of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and 24 mmol of $\text{CO}(\text{NH}_2)_2$ in 70 ml of deionized water (DIW). The values for x should be 0.00, 0.04, 0.12, 0.20, and 0.28 mmol, respectively. The stoichiometric ratio of Cu+Ni to Co was maintained at 1:2. The resulting mixture was then transferred to a 100 mL Teflon-lined autoclave, which underwent hydrothermal treatment at 100°C for 6 h. After the hydrothermal reaction, the sample was equilibrated to ambient temperature, and the resultant precursor underwent a washing process with DIW, followed by ethanol. Subsequently, it was dried in an oven set at 80°C for 10 h to evaporate the solvents. Finally, the dried powder samples of Cu-incorporated NiCo_2O_4 underwent calcination in a muffle furnace at 300°C for 2 h. Upon natural cooling, the synthesized Cu-incorporated NCO nanomaterials with Cu contents of 0.00, 0.04, 0.12, 0.20, and 0.28 mmol were designated as samples CNCOA, CNCOB, CNCOC, CNCOD, and CNCOE, respectively. Additional information on the physicochemical characterization and electrochemical assessments is available in the supplementary materials.

Author Contributions

Periyasamy Sivakumar: conceptualization (lead), data curation (lead), investigation (lead), methodology (lead), validation (lead), writing – original draft (lead). **C. Justin Raj:** methodology (equal), writing – review & editing (equal). **Palaniappan Subramanian:** validation (equal), writing – review & editing (equal). **Antony Dennyson Savariraj:** formal analysis (equal), writing – review & editing (equal). **Ramu Manikandan:** validation (equal), writing – review & editing (equal). **Priti Singh:** data curation (equal), formal analysis (equal), software (equal). **Mudit Dixit:** data curation (equal), formal analysis (lead), software (lead), validation (equal), writing – review & editing (equal). **Hyun Jung:** funding acquisition (lead), resources (lead), writing – review & editing (equal).

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) grant funded by the Korean government (MSIT) (RS-2025-00514396). This work was supported by the project Quantum materials for applications in sustainable technologies (QM4ST), funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004572 by P JAK, call Excellent Research.

Funding

This work was supported by National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF - MSIT) (RS-2025-00514396); P JAK, call Excellent Research (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004572).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

References

1. C. Kovenchan and A.-Y. Lo, “Morphology Engineering of Novel $\text{MnMoO}_4@ \text{NiMoO}_4$ Core-shell Nanostructure as an Electrode Material for Asymmetric Supercapacitor Device,” *Chemical Engineering Journal* 485 (2024): 149950.

2. I. Hussain, A. A. Mahmud, S. Pandiyarajan, et al., “Practicality of MXenes: Recent Trends, Considerations, and Future Aspects in Supercapacitors,” *Materials Today Physics* 55 (2025): 101745.
3. V. K. Sriramadasu, N. Jayababu, and S. Bhattacharyya, “Red Carbon Dots Sensitized Ni-Doped 2D MoS_2 Nanosheets as Electrode Materials for Visible-Light Active Photorechargeable Supercapacitors,” *Small Structures* 6 (2025): 2400480.
4. A. Das, A. Mondal, and B. B. Khatua, “Tuning the Electrochemical Performance of $\text{Cu}_2\text{S}/\text{Co}_3\text{S}_4$ via Optimized CNT Incorporation for High Energy and High Power Supercapacitor Application,” *ACS Applied Energy Materials* 8 (2025): 3812.
5. A. Amiri, L. Vaught, M. Naraghi, and A. A. Polycarpou, “Multifunctional Quasi-Solid-State Zinc-Ion Hybrid Supercapacitors beyond State-of-the-Art Structural Energy Storage,” *Materials Today Physics* 24 (2022): 100654.
6. Q. Zhang, Z. Lin, B. Deng, et al., “Chloride-Ion-Engineered Nickel-Cobalt Bimetallic Chloride: A Tunable Electrode Material for High-Energy-Density Supercapacitors,” *Journal of Power Sources* 633 (2025): 236378.
7. T. Ma, A. Li, J. Hao, T. Hao, and J. Wang, “CTAB Assisted in the Synthesis of Scandium Doped-Induced Oxygen Vacancy Porous CoMoO_4 Positive Electrode and MoO_3 -CNTs Negative Electrode to Construct Ultra-High Performance Supercapacitors,” *Journal of Energy Storage* 121 (2025): 116583.
8. Z. Zhang, S. Wang, K. Hu, et al., “Introducing Ce Into $\text{CuFePBA}@ \text{CuCo-Ldh}$ to Construct Mott-Schottky Heterojunctions with Optimized Electron Redistribution for High-Performance Supercapacitors,” *Advanced Functional Materials* 35 (2025): 2502025.
9. S. D. Dhas, A. C. Mendhe, P. N. Thonge, A. M. Patil, Y. Kim, and D. Kim, “A High-Performance Battery-supercapacitor Hybrid Device and Electrocatalytic Oxygen Evolution Reaction Based on $\text{NiCo}_{2-x}\text{Mn}_x\text{O}_4@ \text{Ni-MOF}$ Ternary Metal Oxide Core-shell Structures,” *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* 12 (2024): 21956.
10. P. Santhoshkumar, D. Vikraman, K. Karuppasamy, R. Manikandan, A. Kathalingam, and H.-S. Kim, “Engineering Time-Dependent MOF-Based Nickel Boride 2D Nanoarchitectures as a Positive Electrode for Energy Storage Applications,” *Applied Surface Science* 661 (2024): 160075.
11. D. Shen, R. Zhang, Y. Ma, et al., “Regulation of Sulfurization Degree: A Strategy to Improve the Electrochemical Performance of $\text{MnCo}_2\text{O}_4@ \text{MnCo}_2\text{S}_4$ Composites in Supercapacitors,” *Chemical Engineering Journal* 513 (2025): 162819.
12. Q. Wei, T. Huang, X. Huang, et al., “High-Rate Sodium-Ion Storage of Vanadium Nitride via Surface-Redox Pseudocapacitance,” *Interdisciplinary Materials* 2 (2023): 434.
13. Y. Geng, S. Bi, J. Zhang, et al., *ACS Applied Nano Materials* 8 (2025): 5218.
14. M. He, J. Qiao, B. Zhou, et al., “Controllable Metal-Organic Framework-Derived NiCo -Layered Double Hydroxide Nanosheets on Vertical Graphene as Mott-Schottky Heterostructure for High-Performance Hybrid Supercapacitor,” *Small Structures* 5 (2024): 2400207.
15. Z. Pan, K. Li, L. Sun, et al., “A High-Concentration Edge-Nitrogen-Doped Porous Carbon Anode via Template Free Strategy for High-Performance Potassium-Ion Hybrid Capacitors,” *Energy Material Advances* 5 (2024): 0080.
16. Z. Wang, F. Tang, T. Li, et al., “ RuO_2 Nanoclusters Embedded Bunch-Like Co_3O_4 Nanowire Array on Nickel Foam for High Performance Asymmetric Supercapacitors,” *Journal of Power Sources* 644 (2025): 237118.
17. N. Kumar, M. R. Ansari, S. Khaladkar, et al., “ CuFe_2O_4 Nanoparticles as Potential Electrode Material for Asymmetric Supercapacitor Applications,” *Journal of Power Sources* 642 (2025): 236960.

18. H. Gao, X. Li, and Y. Ma, "Nickel Cobaltate/Nickel Cobalt Layered Double Hydroxide Composites as Electrodes for Asymmetric Flexible Supercapacitors," *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* 695 (2025): 137802.
19. Y. Fu, X. Wang, W. Feng, et al., "Modulation of the Structure and Morphology of NiCo₂S₄ by Varying the Anion Types of Nickel and Cobalt Salts to Achieve High-Rate Supercapacitive Performance," *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* 687 (2025): 197.
20. Z. Zhang, S. Sun, Z. Xu, and S. Yin, "Multicomponent Hybridization Transition Metal Oxide Electrode Enriched with Oxygen Vacancy for Ultralong-Life Supercapacitor," *Small* 19 (2023): 2302479.
21. H. Ansarinejad, M. Shabani-Nooshabadi, and S. M. Ghoreishi, "Introducing of WO₃@NiCo₂O₄/rGO Ternary Nanocomposites as Active Material for High-Performance Supercapacitor Applications," *Journal of Energy Storage* 74 (2023): 109256.
22. S. Prabhu, M. Maruthapandi, A. Durairaj, et al., "Performances of Co²⁺-Substituted NiMoO₄ Nanorods in a Solid-State Hybrid Supercapacitor," *ACS Applied Energy Materials* 6 (2023): 1321.
23. J. Kuang, Z. Liu, L. Fu, et al., "Charge Tuning and Anchor Effect Achieving Stable High-Voltage Layered Metal Oxides for Sodium-Ion Battery," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 64 (2025): e202500715.
24. X. Hong, H. You, C. Deng, G. Wang, and W. Dong, "Optimization of Al-Doped NiCo₂O₄ Hybrid Nanostructures and Their Electrochemical Activation Feature in Supercapacitors," *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 1002 (2024): 175239.
25. W. Hu, B. Hu, Z. Wu, et al., "Exceeding 50 000 Cycle Durability of Layered Hydroxide-Based Hybrid Supercapacitor Through Scandium Doping-Induced Superlong Activation Process," *Small Structures* 5 (2024): 2300574.
26. S. A. Ahmad, F. Mashkoor, M. A. Ansari, A. A. Allothman, M. Shoeb, and C. Jeong, "Morus Alba-Mediated Defect-Rich Fe-Doped V₂O₅ Nanoparticles on Woven Carbon Fiber for High-Performance Supercapacitor with Enhanced Charge Storage Mechanism," *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 1020 (2025): 179515.
27. P. J. Sharma, K. K. Joshi, S. Siraj, P. Sahatiya, C. K. Sumesh, and P. M. Pataniya, "Vanadium-Doped Ni₃S₂: Morphological Evolution for Enhanced Industrial-Scale Water and Urea Electrolysis," *ChemSusChem* 18 (2025): e202401371.
28. J. He, Y. Zhou, S. Wu, et al., "Cr-Substituted SrCoO_{3-δ} Perovskite with Abundant Oxygen Vacancies for High-Energy and Durable Low-Temperature Antifreezing Flexible Supercapacitor," *Inorganic Chemistry* 63 (2024): 13755.
29. G. Liu, Y. Liu, J. Luo, et al., "Surface Corrosion Engineering Endows Mn-Doped NiCo₂O₄ Nanosheets with High Capacity and Long Life for Alkaline Zn-Based Batteries," *ACS Applied Energy Materials* 7 (2024): 2234.
30. D. Shen, R. Zhang, S. Liu, et al., "Synthesis of Urchin-Like MnCo₂O₄ Nanospheres as Electrode Material for Supercapacitors," *Journal of Energy Storage* 105 (2025): 114775.
31. Y. Wang, P. Liu, K. Zhu, J. Wang, and J. Liu, "Hierarchical Bilayered Hybrid Nanostructural Arrays of NiCo₂O₄ Micro-Urchins and Nanowires as a Free-Standing Electrode with High Loading for High-Performance Lithium-Ion Batteries," *Nanoscale* 9 (2017): 14979.
32. R. Priyadharsini, C. Manoharan, M. Bououdina, S. Sagadevan, M. Venkateshwarlu, and S. A. Bahadur, "Impact of Nickel Substitution on Structural, Dielectric, Magnetic, and Electrochemical Properties of Copper Ferrite Nanostructures for Energy Storage Devices," *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* 653 (2024): 917.
33. A. Hroub, M. H. Aleinawi, M. Stefan, et al., "Vanadium-Doped Magnesium Oxide Nanoparticles as Electrodes in Supercapacitor Devices," *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 958 (2023): 170442.
34. I. Sabir, H. Mingxia, H. Anwar, M. Kashif, and Z. Yizhu, "Utilization of Copper-Doped Zinc Spinel Ferrites Nano-Composites as Battery-Grade Electrode Materials for Supercapattery Device Applications," *Journal of Energy Storage* 112 (2025): 115498.
35. R. Sukanya, R. Karthik, A. A. Mahmud, et al., "Vanadium-Doped MoSe₂ Nanosheets: Induced Lattice Contraction and Enhanced Conductivity for Superior Hydrogen Evolution Reaction," *Electrochemistry Communications* 175 (2025): 107916.
36. J. Zheng, X. Peng, Z. Xu, J. Gong, and Z. Wang, "Cationic Defect Engineering in Spinel NiCo₂O₄ for Enhanced Electrocatalytic Oxygen Evolution," *ACS Catalysis* 12 (2022): 10245.
37. T. V. Nguyen, L. T. Son, V. V. Thuy, et al., "Facile Synthesis of Mn-Doped NiCo₂O₄ Nanoparticles with Enhanced Electrochemical Performance for a Battery-Type Supercapacitor Electrode," *Dalton Transactions* 49 (2020): 6718.
38. R. Lather and P. Jeevanandam, "Iron-Doped NiCo₂O₄ Nanoparticles: Synthesis via Homogeneous Precipitation Method and Studies on Their Peroxidase-Like Activity," *European Journal of Inorganic Chemistry* 2022 (2022): e202200387.
39. G. M. Kumar, V. Ganesh, D. J. Lee, et al., "Fabrication of Zn_{1-x}Ni_xWO₄ Nanorods with Superior Photoelectrochemical and Photocatalytic Performances," *Ceramics International* 48 (2022): 29438.
40. P. Kumcham, T. V. M. Sreekanth, K. Yoo, and J. Kim, "Construction of Cationic Vacancy-Rich Mulberry-Like MnCo₂O_{4,5} Nanostructures with High Surface Area for High-Performance Hybrid Supercapacitors," *ACS Applied Energy Materials* 7 (2024): 11754.
41. M. Geerthana, J. Archana, E. S. Kumar, and M. Navaneethan, "Unveiling the Potential of Copper-Doped Metal Oxides: A Novel Strategy for High-Capacity Hybrid Supercapatteries with Enhanced Power, Energy Density, and Cycling Stability," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 121 (2025): 228.
42. D. S. Nair, A. Anil, L. Elias, N. Satyanarayana, H. K. Holla, and S. M. A. Shibli, "Tuning of Physicochemical and Electronic Characteristics of Cu-Doped NiCo₂O₄ Ternary Inverse Spinel Oxides for Effective Electrocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution Reaction," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 62 (2024): 162.
43. M. R. Thalji, G. A. M. Ali, J.-J. Shim, and K. F. Chong, "Cobalt-Doped Tungsten Suboxides for Supercapacitor Applications," *Chemical Engineering Journal* 473 (2023): 145341.
44. F. F. Alharbi, M. S. Waheed, S. Aman, N. Ahmad, H. M. T. Farid, and T. A. Mohaymen Taha, "Facile Development of Mn Doped NiO Nanoarrays Supported on a Reduced Graphene Oxide Nanocomposite as a Supercapacitor," *Energy & Fuels* 37 (2023): 12225.
45. P. Sivakumar, C. J. Raj, H. Jung, and H. S. Park, "2D/2D Nanoarchitecture of Ni/NiCo₂O₄ Deposited onto Reduced Graphene Oxide for High-Performance Hybrid Supercapacitor Applications," *Journal of Energy Storage* 69 (2023): 107946.
46. P. Naveenkumar, J. Yesuraj, M. Maniyazagan, H.-W. Yang, K. Kim, and S.-J. Kim, "Synthesis of MoS₂ Nanosheet-Encapsulated CuCo₂S₄ Nanoparticle Clusters Derived from Metal Glycerate for High-Performance Supercapacitor Applications," *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 1014 (2025): 178737.
47. B. Wang, W. Jia, M. Liu, et al., "One Step Glow-Discharge Electrolysis-Based Preparation of Al Doped Ni-Co Layered Double Hydroxide/Graphene Oxide as Supercapacitor Electrode Material," *Chemical Engineering Journal* 500 (2024): 157622.
48. R.-H. Qiao, B. Zhang, S.-Q. Wang, X.-M. Luo, and G.-P. Zhang, "Phosphate-Modified NiCo₂O₄@NiCoS Heterointerface Boosting Electrochemical Performance for Supercapacitors," *ACS Applied Energy Materials* 7 (2024): 8014.
49. A. H. Al-Naggar, V. V. Jadhav, S. F. Shaikh, R. Ali, and R. S. Mane, "Enhanced Charge Storage Performance and Electrocatalytic Oxygen

Evolution Reaction Activity of Self-Grown Iron–Cobalt-Doped Nickel Oxide Nanoplates: An Example of the Synergistic Effect,” *Energy & Fuels* 38 (2024): 23699.

50. J. Ma, E. Guo, and L. Yin, “Porous Hierarchical Spinel Mn-Doped NiCo₂O₄ Nanosheet Architectures as High-Performance Anodes for Lithium-Ion Batteries and Electrochemical Reaction Mechanism,” *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics* 30 (2019): 8555.

51. S. Jangu, S. Kumar, K. N. Deepika, C. Jacob, and D. Pradhan, “Effect of Microwave Power and Cu Doping on MnO₂ Nanostructures and Its Supercapacitor Performance,” *ACS Applied Electronic Materials* 5 (2023): 3078.

52. Y. Wang, Z. Meng, X. Gong, et al., “Enhancing Stability of Co₉S₈ by Iron Incorporation for Oxygen Evolution Reaction and Supercapacitor Electrodes,” *Chemical Engineering Journal* 431 (2022): 133980.

53. S. Maheshwaram, S. Gaddameedi, S. C. Chidurala, et al., “Enhanced Structural and Electrochemical Properties of Zn-Doped NiCo₂O₄ Synthesized by Low-Temperature Microwave Hydrothermal Process,” *ECS Journal of Solid State Science and Technology* 12 (2023): 093008.

54. Z. Zhang, Y. Cheng, H. Li, Z. Xu, S. Sun, and S. Yin, “Construction of Cu-Doped Ni–Co-Based Electrodes for High-Performance Supercapacitor Applications,” *ACS Applied Energy Materials* 5 (2022): 6642.

55. Z. Zhu, F. Chen, M. Yang, et al., “Effect of F-Doped ZnWO₄ Electrodes with Oxygen Vacancies on High-Performance Asymmetric Supercapacitors,” *Journal of Energy Storage* 118 (2025): 116264.

56. Y. Yan, W. Wu, Y. Yang, T. Xu, and X. Li, “Controlled Hierarchical Construction of Ultrahomogeneous Co₉S₈@CoAl-LDH/NF Layered Core-Shell Heterostructures for High-Performance Asymmetric Supercapacitors,” *Inorganic Chemistry* 63 (2024): 23276.

57. H. Zhao, L. Liu, X. Xiao, et al., “The Effects of Co Doping on the Crystal Structure and Electrochemical Performance of Mg(Mn_{2-x}Co_x)O₄ Negative Materials for Lithium Ion Battery,” *Solid State Sciences* 39 (2015): 23.

58. Y. Ma, C. Fang, B. Ding, G. Ji, and J. Y. Lee, “Fe-Doped Mn_xO_y with Hierarchical Porosity as a High-Performance Lithium-Ion Battery Anode,” *Advanced Materials* 25 (2013): 4646.

59. C. Chen, Y. Huang, C. An, et al., “Copper-Doped Dual Phase Li₄Ti₅O₁₂-TiO₂ Nanosheets as High-Rate and Long Cycle Life Anodes for High-Power Lithium-Ion Batteries,” *ChemSusChem* 8 (2015): 114.

60. M. R. Pallavolu, K. G. Krishna, G. Nagaraju, P. S. S. Babu, S. Sambasivam, and A. Sreedhar, “Rational Design of Cu-Doped Co₃O₄@carbon Nanocomposite and Agriculture Crop-Waste Derived Activated Carbon for High-Performance Hybrid Supercapacitors,” *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry* 116 (2022): 428.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Supporting Fig. S1:** SEM images at various magnification levels of (a-c) CNCOB, (d-f) CNCOC, and (g-i) CNCOE nano/microarchitectural materials. **Supporting Fig. S2:** SEM-EDS elemental mapping images of (a) (i-iv) CNCOA, (b) (i-v) CNCOB, (c) (i-v) CNCOC, (d) (i-v) CNCOD, and (e) (i-v) CNCOE nano/microarchitectural materials. **Supporting Fig. S3:** TEM-EDS elemental mapping images of (a) (i-iv) CNCOA and (b) (i-v) CNCOD nano/microarchitectural materials. **Supporting Fig. S4:** XPS full-scan spectra of CNCOA and CNCOD nanomaterials, (b) BET isotherms graph, and (c) BJH pore size distribution plots of CNCOB, CNCOC, and CNCOE nanomaterials. **Supporting Fig. S5:** (a) Comparative analysis of CVs at a constant scan speed of 30 mV/s, (b) the Nyquist impedance plots of CNCO electrode materials, and (c) broadened perspective of the Nyquist impedance plots in the high-frequency area. **Supporting Fig. S6:** CVs at different sweep rates from 5 to 50 mV/s: (a) CNCOA, (b) CNCOB, (c) CNCOC, and (d) CNCOE electrode materials. **Supporting Fig. S7:** The plot of peak current vs. log of sweep rates at different scan rates, the CVs of contributions from both

the capacitive and diffusive regions at 50 mV/s, and the effect of different sweep rates on the contributions of surface-governed and diffusive-controlled capacitance processes in the (a-c) CNCOA and (d-f) CNCOD electrodes. **Supporting Fig. S8:** GCD profiles at current different densities ranging from 1 to 20 A/g: (a) CNCOA, (b) CNCOB, (c) CNCOC, and (d) CNCOE electrode materials. **Supporting Fig. S9:** Assessing the specific capacitance as a function of varying current densities: (a) CNCOA, (b) CNCOB, (c) CNCOC, and (d) CNCOE electrode materials. **Supporting Fig. S10:** (a) CVs of the AC and CNCOD electrodes in three electrode configurations at a constant scan rate of 50 mV/s, (b) CV characteristics of AC performance across varied sweep rates ranging from 10 to 100 mV/s, (c) CVs of the BSH system at different voltage ranges, and (d) GCD profiles of the BSH system across varied voltage windows. **Supporting Fig. S11:** Physicochemical characterizations of the CNCOD electrode after the long-term stability test: (a) XRD pattern of CNCOD electrode material after stability test with standard pattern, and (b-d) SEM images at different magnifications of the CNCOD electrode material after stability test.